

1 **Functional Dissection and Evidence for Intercellular Transfer of the**
2 **Heterocyst-Differentiation PatS Morphogen**

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16 **Summary**

17 The formation of a diazotrophic cyanobacterial filament represents a simple
18 example of biological development. In *Anabaena*, a non-random pattern of one
19 nitrogen-fixing heterocyst separated by about 10 photosynthetic vegetative cells
20 results from lateral inhibition elicited by the cells differentiating into heterocysts.
21 Key to this process is the *patS* gene, which has been shown to produce an inhibitor
22 of heterocyst differentiation that involves the C-terminal RGSGR pentapeptide.
23 Complementation of a $\Delta patS$ *Anabaena* mutant with different versions of PatS,
24 including point mutations or tag fusions, showed that *patS* is translated into a 17-
25 amino acid polypeptide. Alterations in the N-terminal part of PatS produced
26 inhibition of heterocyst differentiation, thus this part of the peptide appears
27 necessary for proper processing and self-immunity in the producing cells.
28 Alterations in the C-terminal part of PatS led to over-differentiation, thus
29 supporting its role in inhibition of heterocyst differentiation. A polypeptide,
30 produced in proheterocysts, consisting of a methionine followed by the eight, but
31 not the five, terminal amino acids of PatS recreated the full activity of the native
32 peptide. Immunofluorescence detection showed that an RGSGR-containing peptide
33 accumulated in the cells adjacent to the producing proheterocysts, illustrating
34 intercellular transfer of a morphogen in the cyanobacterial filaments.

35

36 **Introduction**

37 In the living world, multicellularity appears to have arisen several times during the
38 course of evolution (Bonner, 1998). Communal behaviors that provide benefit to a

39 group involving communication, cooperative behavior and molecular exchange
40 between cells are frequent in bacteria (Dunny, 2008; Manteca and Sánchez, 2009).
41 Nevertheless, filamentous heterocyst-forming cyanobacteria represent a further
42 step in multicellularity based on a structured supracellular organization including
43 different interdependent cell types, each specialized in a different nutritional task,
44 that contribute to the growth of the filament as the organismic unit (Flores and
45 Herrero, 2010; Kumar *et al.*, 2010). This organization can be traced back at least 2
46 billion years, before multicellularity appeared in eukaryotes (see Tomitani *et al.*,
47 2006; Schirromeister *et al.*, 2011).

48 Heterocyst differentiation represents a remarkable solution for the co-
49 occurrence of the incompatible processes of oxygenic photosynthesis and N₂
50 fixation. Cyanobacteria ancestors developed oxygenic photosynthesis and played a
51 crucial role in the evolution of the biosphere, including the oxidation of the Earth's
52 atmosphere 2.22-2.45 billion years ago and the establishment of symbiotic
53 associations leading to the development of algal and plant plastids (Knoll, 2008).
54 While endorsing the cyanobacterial ancestors with a unique trait of using sunlight
55 and water to generate energy for living, the development of oxygenic
56 photosynthesis represented a burden for the use of atmospheric N₂ as a source of
57 nitrogen for growth due to the general sensitivity of the nitrogenase system to
58 oxygen. In some filamentous cyanobacteria some of the cells in the filament
59 differentiate into specialized cells, called heterocysts, where the N₂-fixation system
60 is confined, so that the vegetative cells perform oxygenic photosynthesis driving
61 photosynthetic CO₂ fixation, whereas heterocysts rely on a mainly heterotrophic
62 metabolism to carry out the fixation of atmospheric N₂. Vegetative cells provide
63 heterocysts with reduced C to serve as source of energy and reductant, whereas

64 heterocysts transfer combined nitrogen to the vegetative cells (Flores and Herrero,
65 2010; Wolk *et al.*, 1994).

66 Heterocyst differentiation requires the action of a number of regulators,
67 being pivotal the N-control transcription factor NtcA, a member of the CRP-family
68 of regulators, and the differentiation-specific protein HetR, which is also a
69 transcription factor (Flores and Herrero, 2010; Kumar *et al.*, 2010; Kim *et al.*, 2011;
70 Herrero *et al.*, 2013). Heterocysts are found in a non-random distribution along
71 the filament (Wolk *et al.*, 1994). In the case of strains of the genera *Anabaena* or
72 *Nostoc*, heterocysts are distributed at semi-regular intervals separated by ca. 10-
73 15 vegetative cells. Nutritionally, this pattern appears to respond to the constraints
74 imposed by the limited number of vegetative cells that can be fed by each
75 heterocyst and the limited number of cells that can be dispensed of contributing to
76 CO₂ fixation. When filaments growing with combined nitrogen are subjected to
77 nitrogen step-down, that pattern is established early, much before heterocyst
78 maturation has been completed (Yoon and Golden, 2001). Thus, during this
79 developmental process, positional information is generated before N₂ fixation has
80 started.

81 A product of the *patS* gene has been implicated in establishing the spatial
82 pattern of heterocyst distribution after nitrogen deprivation (Yoon and Golden,
83 1998, 2001). The gene is induced early in the differentiating cells and its
84 inactivation leads to a Mch (Multiple contiguous heterocysts) phenotype, whereas
85 its over-expression abolishes differentiation. In *Anabaena* sp. strain PCC 7120 the
86 *patS* gene would encode a 17- or 13-amino acid peptide of which a subset
87 consisting of the 5 C-terminal amino acids (RGSGR, a peptide called PatS-5)

88 inhibits differentiation when added to the external medium, although it fails to
89 restore a wild-type heterocyst pattern on a *patS* mutant (Yoon and Golden, 1998).
90 In vitro, PatS-5 has been shown to interact with HetR and to inhibit binding of
91 HetR to DNA upstream from several regulated genes (Huang *et al.*, 2004; Risser
92 and Callahan, 2007; Du *et al.*, 2012; Feldmann *et al.*, 2011). It is considered that
93 PatS, or a processed derivative of it, is exported from the differentiating cells to
94 inhibit the differentiation of its neighbors likely by acting on the transcription
95 factor HetR (Yoon and Golden, 1998; Khudyakov and Golden, 2004; Risser and
96 Callahan, 2009). However, information about the identity of the primary gene
97 product and of the molecule actually acting as a trans-cellular inhibitor of
98 differentiation, thus behaving as a morphogen, as well as about the in vivo
99 processing, is lacking.

100 In this work we present evidence for the synthesis of a 17-amino acid PatS
101 in (pro)heterocysts. Adhering to definitions by C. P. Wolk, in *Anabaena*, a
102 proheterocyst is an intermediate, between a vegetative cell and a heterocyst, that
103 differs in shape and granularity from vegetative cells, and a mature heterocyst is a
104 cell capable of aerobic fixation of N₂ (see Wolk *et al.*, 1994). We also show that the
105 C-terminal octapeptide, but not the C-terminal heptapeptide, hexapeptide or
106 pentapeptide, of PatS is sufficient for regulation of heterocyst patterning along the
107 filament. Specific residues in the N-terminal part of PatS are crucial for self-
108 immunity in the producing cells, likely reflecting their role in PatS processing
109 and/or export, whereas specific C-terminal amino acids determine the heterocyst
110 differentiation inhibitory activity of the peptide. Additionally, using an
111 immunofluorescence approach, we have detected the in vivo location of PatS.

112 **Results**

113 To better mimic the physiological conditions, we have chosen to express a number
114 of versions of the *patS* gene from the native *patS* promoter in the chromosome
115 (Fig. 1). In support of this approach, a recent report documents an extensive copy-
116 number variability of heterologous replicons commonly used in strain PCC 7120
117 (Yang *et al.*, 2012). The engineered *patS* gene was transferred by conjugation from
118 *Escherichia coli* to *Anabaena* sp. strain CSVT20, a derivative of strain PCC 7120 in
119 which the wild-type *patS* gene has been deleted. In this way, strains in which only
120 the altered version of *patS* is present were generated (Table 1). Because strain
121 CSVT20, like other *patS* deletion strains (Yoon and Golden, 1998), produces a Mch
122 phenotype, which correlates with a disinhibition of heterocyst formation, this
123 approach permitted a simple test of phenotypic complementation. As shown
124 below, three basic phenotypes were observed with the altered *patS* genes: lack of
125 complementation retaining the $\Delta patS$ Mch phenotype, complementation resulting
126 in a wild-type phenotype, and complete or partial inhibition of heterocyst
127 differentiation.

128 *Expression of PatS-17*

129 As mentioned above, the *patS* ORF could encode a 17- or 13-amino acid peptide,
130 which depends on whether translation starts at the first or the second possible
131 Met-encoding codon. We have studied translation initiation of the *patS* gene
132 monitoring fluorescence emission from strains bearing the *gfp-mut2* gene (lacking
133 its start codon) inserted in phase after the 1st (strain CSL21) or the 5th (strain
134 CSL19) triplet of the *patS* ORF. As a reference of the time-course activation of the
135 *patS* promoter, we monitored GFP fluorescence from strain CSVM17 (Mariscal *et*

136 *al.*, 2007), a derivative of strain PCC 7120 bearing a transcriptional P_{patS} -*gfp* fusion
137 inserted in a neutral region of the *Anabaena* α megaplasmid, which has the same
138 copy number as the chromosome (Lee *et al.*, 2003). The GFP fluorescence was
139 monitored in filaments grown with ammonium and subjected to combined-
140 nitrogen deprivation. Strains CSL21 and CSL19 both produced GFP fluorescence,
141 localized to specific cells (Fig. 2), indicating that the first Met codon can be used as
142 a translation start of the *patS* gene.

143 *Phenotype of strains bearing GFP- and 6His-tag-fusions*

144 In addition to the strains producing PatS-GFP fusions, we studied a strain derived
145 from the *patS* mutant CSVT20 that bears a modified *patS* gene encoding a PatS
146 version with a 6His sequence inserted between M⁵ and L⁶ of the polypeptide
147 (strain CSL22). Phenotypic characteristics of strains CSL19, CSL21, and CSL22 with
148 regard to the frequency and distribution of proheterocysts plus heterocysts,
149 expression of nitrogenase activity and ability to grow diazotrophically (Table 2)
150 were studied using strains PCC 7120 and CSVT20 as controls. In all the mutant
151 strains generated in this work, proheterocysts and heterocysts were visualized by
152 Alcian Blue staining that colors the Hep layer of the heterocyst envelope (see
153 López-Igual *et al.*, 2012b). The data of percentage of total heterocysts, with regard
154 to total cells, and of contiguous heterocysts, as well as the distribution of sizes of
155 vegetative cell intervals between heterocysts, are shown in Figure 3 and
156 summarized in Table 1.

157 Strain CSL21 (GFP inserted after M¹) exhibited a (pro)heterocyst frequency
158 of 2.94% of the total cells (the wild type has 10.31% and the control strain CSL48,
159 bearing the wild-type *patS* sequence construct, has 12.39%) (Table 1), very low

160 nitrogenase activity and impaired diazotrophic growth (Table 2). Strain CSL19
161 (GFP inserted after M⁵) exhibited a very low (pro)heterocyst frequency (0.54% of
162 the total cells) and, consistent with a very low nitrogenase activity, a very low
163 diazotrophic growth rate. Strain CSL22 (6His sequence inserted after M⁵) exhibited
164 a (pro)heterocyst frequency of 5.31% of total cells. In this strain, nitrogenase
165 activity and diazotrophic growth rate were also lower than in the wild type,
166 although the impairment in diazotrophic growth was less pronounced than in
167 CSL21. Thus, insertion of GFP after M¹ (strain CSL21) or of 6His (strain CSL22) or
168 GFP (strain CSL19) after M⁵ leads to impairment in heterocyst differentiation,
169 which is most severe in the latter case. These results are consistent with the idea
170 that the modified forms of PatS expressed in strains CSL19, CSL21 and CSL22
171 inhibit differentiation of the producing cells.

172 *Point amino acid mutations of patS*

173 Strains expressing versions of PatS with point amino acid substitutions in each
174 position of the peptide were also investigated (Table 1 and Fig. 3). Whereas
175 substitution M⁵A (present in strain CSL49) had little effect on (pro)heterocyst
176 frequency or distribution with respect to the wild type or the CSL48 control strain,
177 substitution M¹A (in strain CSL44) produced a *patS* phenotype. These results
178 indicate that M¹ is necessary and sufficient as a translation start of *patS*.

179 In strain CSL90 (K²A) (pro)heterocyst frequency was 4.47% of total cells,
180 whereas in strains CSL91 (A³Q) and CSL92 (I⁴Q) it was 2.10 and 1.97%,
181 respectively. Substitution L⁶Q (in strain CSL50) had almost no effect on
182 (pro)heterocyst frequency or interval-size distribution. Substitution V⁷Q (in strain
183 CSL51) abolished differentiation whereas V⁷A (strain CSL93) led to a

184 (pro)heterocyst frequency of 3.43%. These results can be interpreted in terms of
185 inhibition of differentiation in the cells producing PatS with the indicated changes,
186 except for the one in L⁶. Additionally, results with strain CSL51 together with the
187 behavior of strain CSL62 (M⁵V, V⁷Q), which showed a frequency of
188 (pro)heterocysts of 6.01%, indicated that V⁷ has a critical role to prevent an
189 inhibitory activity of PatS in the producing cells, and that this role could be
190 partially served by the presence of a V residue in the 5th position of PatS.

191 Substitutions N⁸E (strain CSL52) and F⁹Q (strain CSL53) also lowered the
192 frequency of (pro)heterocysts (8.35% and 7.45% of total cells, respectively) and
193 the frequency of (pro)heterocysts consecutive to another (pro)heterocyst (interval
194 size = 0) (1.33% of the total intervals in strain CSL52 and no doublets detected in
195 strain CSL53; 6.01% in the control strain CSL48). Moreover, in strain CSL53 the
196 mean interval size between heterocysts (14.01 cells) was somewhat higher than in
197 the control strain (10.40 cells). Thus, N⁸ and F⁹ appear to influence prevention of
198 inhibition by PatS in the producing cells.

199 Some amino acid substitutions in the C-terminal part of PatS, including
200 PatS-5, blocked the PatS inhibitory activity. The R¹³A (in strain CSL57) and S¹⁵A (in
201 strain CSL58) changes increased (pro)heterocyst frequency and shortened
202 vegetative cell intervals between (pro)heterocysts to levels comparable to those of
203 strain CSVT20; the G¹⁶A change (in strain CSL60) considerably increased
204 (pro)heterocyst frequency (although to a lesser extent than in strains CSL57 or
205 CSL58) and shortened intervals; and the G¹⁴A (in strain CSL59) and R¹⁷A (in strain
206 CSL61) changes produced increases in pro(heterocyst) frequency similar to that in
207 CSL60 and an alteration in the distribution of (pro)heterocysts less drastic,

208 specially concerning the frequency of contiguous heterocysts, than that in strain
209 CSL60. Substitutions C¹⁰A (strain CSL54) and E¹²A (strain CSL56) increased the
210 frequency of doublets (about 11.15% and 9.08%, respectively), whereas
211 substitution D¹¹Q (strain CSL55) had very little effect on the studied parameters.
212 Thus, residues R¹³, S¹⁵ and G¹⁶ appear to be essential and G¹⁴ and R¹⁷, and to a
213 lesser extent C¹⁰ and E¹², important for PatS activity (i.e., inhibition of heterocyst
214 differentiation).

215 *patS minigenes*

216 To compare the activity of the PatS-5 peptide and that of peptides including the
217 residues that we had found to influence the activity of PatS (i.e. whose mutation
218 led to over-differentiation), strains that produce short versions of PatS consisting
219 of a Met residue plus the C-terminal RGSGR pentapeptide (strain CSL45), ERGSGR
220 hexapeptide (strain CSL46), DERGSGR heptapeptide (strain CSL94) or CDERGSGR
221 octapeptide (strain CSL47) were constructed. As a control, strain CSL48 produces
222 the full 17-aa PatS. In contrast to *patS* minigenes that have been investigated
223 previously, which were provided in a multicopy plasmid (Wu *et al.*, 2004), our
224 constructs were present in the native *patS* locus in the chromosome (Fig. 1).
225 (Pro)heterocyst frequency and distribution in strain CSL47 were similar to those
226 in CSL48 and the wild-type strains. This observation indicates that the C-terminal
227 octapeptide of PatS has an effect close to that of the full PatS gene product. In
228 contrast, strain CSL45 showed a frequency of (pro)heterocysts and mean size of
229 vegetative cell intervals between (pro)heterocysts similar to those of the *patS*
230 mutant strain CSVT20, and a frequency of contiguous heterocysts intermediate
231 between those of the control CSL48 and strain CSVT20. In strain CSL46, the

232 frequency of (pro)heterocysts and the mean interval size are between the values of
233 the wild type and the *patS* mutant, and the frequency of contiguous heterocysts is
234 similar to that of this mutant. Finally, in strain CSL94 the frequency of
235 (pro)heterocysts and the mean interval size are similar to the wild-type values,
236 and the frequency of contiguous heterocysts is between the wild-type and the *patS*
237 mutant value. Thus, strain CSL45 exhibits low, if any, PatS inhibitory activity,
238 whereas strains CSL46 and CSL94 appears to exhibit partial PatS activity.

239 *Detection of PatS by immunofluorescence*

240 The detection of PatS or PatS-derived peptides in *Anabaena* sp. strain PCC 7120
241 was undertaken by immunofluorescence using antibodies raised against synthetic
242 PatS-5 (see Experimental Procedures). Ammonium-grown filaments of the wild
243 type and strains CSVT20 and CSL45 were incubated 8 h in the absence of combined
244 nitrogen and treated to detect fluorescence from PatS-5 antibodies. As revealed by
245 Alcian Blue staining (not shown), (pro)heterocysts could already be detected in the
246 culture. The fluorescence obtained from strain CSVT20, which lacks a *patS* gene, is
247 presented in Figure 4 as a reference background. Although this strain
248 differentiates heterocysts, no cell exhibiting high fluorescence was observed. In
249 filaments of wild-type strain PCC 7120, fluorescence was detected in a number of
250 cells at levels above the background levels observed in the cells of strain CSVT20.
251 As a representative example, the filament of strain PCC 7120 shown in Figure 4A
252 bears three cells with the morphology of proheterocysts, in which the fluorescence
253 detected was lower than in their neighboring vegetative cells. The distribution of
254 fluorescence in proheterocysts and the cells occupying neighboring positions 1 to
255 7 with regard to proheterocysts is shown in Fig. 4B. The data indicates that, on

256 average, in strain PCC 7120 fluorescence in proheterocysts is similar to the
257 background levels, and it is higher in the cells contiguous to proheterocysts.
258 Indeed, fluorescence appears to decrease gradually from the first to, at least, the
259 fifth neighbor. Because the *patS* gene is expressed in proheterocysts (Yoon and
260 Golden 1998, 2001), and indeed in our experiments *patS* is expressed mainly in
261 single cells at the 8 h time point after N step-down (see strain CSVM17 in Fig. 2),
262 even in the event that (pro)heterocyst labeling with the antibodies were less
263 effective than labeling of vegetative cells, our results show accumulation of a PatS
264 peptide in non-producing cells adjacent to the producing proheterocysts. The
265 observed spatial pattern of fluorescence is consistent with an export of PatS from
266 the producing proheterocyst and further vegetative cell-to-vegetative cell
267 transference. Also, the fact that no cell with fluorescence above the background
268 was observed in strain CSVT20 speaks against detection of other PatS-5-containing
269 proteins (e.g., HetN) under the used conditions.

270 As described above, strain CSL45 produces a version of PatS (Met-PatS-5)
271 that apparently lacks PatS function, since heterocyst differentiation is disinhibited
272 in this strain. Figure 4A shows two short filaments of CSL45 that contain
273 proheterocysts, which in the immunofluorescence analysis showed higher
274 fluorescence than their neighboring vegetative cells. Thus, in contrast to what
275 happened in the wild type, the Met-PatS-5 peptide produced in strain CSL45 was
276 apparently retained in the producing cells. Quantification of fluorescence in strain
277 CSL45 showed that, on average, the PatS immunofluorescence signal is high in cells
278 that could be identified as proheterocysts and in cells occupying the 1 to 3
279 neighboring positions, and considerably lower beyond that position (Fig. 4B). In
280 this strain, the high PatS signal in cell clusters may reflect the pattern of the *patS*

281 gene expression, consistent with the observed high frequency of contiguous
282 heterocysts (see Table 1). (Results obtained with strain CSL45 also shows that PatS
283 could be already detected in 8-hour proheterocysts.)

284 **Discussion**

285 The *patS* gene is a key player in the establishment of the spatial pattern of
286 development that takes place in response to nitrogen deprivation in the filaments
287 of heterocyst-forming cyanobacteria, such as the model organism *Anabaena* sp.
288 strain PCC 7120. Despite a considerable amount of recent work dealing with the
289 effects of, mainly, the pentapeptide corresponding to the 5-residue C-terminal
290 fragment of PatS, PatS-5, little is known about how PatS is processed and which is
291 the actual molecule active as a morphogen in vivo. In this work, we have
292 constructed a number of *Anabaena* strains expressing, as the only version and
293 from the native *patS* promoter in the chromosome, variants of the *patS* gene. These
294 include genes encoding PatS with a 6His-tag or GFP insertions or with amino-acid
295 substitutions and minigenes encoding different extents of the C-terminal part of
296 PatS.

297 The first and fifth codons of the strain PCC 7120 *patS* ORF (Kaneko *et al.*,
298 2001) are Met-encoding codons, which until now made it uncertain the identity of
299 the translation start of the *patS* gene product. Our results indicate that the first of
300 these codons is the principal *patS* translational start. First, when *gfp* is inserted in
301 frame after the first Met-encoding codon (in strain CSL21), GFP fluorescence is
302 observed in cells with a specific distribution along the filament, indicating that M¹
303 is readily used as a translational start. Second, the change M¹A (in strain CSL44)
304 results in a phenotype of percentage and distribution of (pro)heterocysts similar

305 to that of the *patS* null mutant (strain CSV20), whereas substitution M⁵A (in
306 strain CSL49) produces little changes compared to the wild type, indicating that
307 M¹, but not M⁵, is required for PatS function. Finally, strain CSL21 shows a
308 considerable decrease in heterocyst frequency and nitrogenase activity as
309 compared to the wild type, indicating that alteration of the amino acid stretch
310 preceding M⁵ by introduction of the GFP interferes with PatS function. Due to its
311 small size, the presence of *patS* genes in genomic sequences is difficult to predict in
312 the absence of experimental analysis. However, searching for RGSGR in the
313 chromosomes of 13 heterocyst-forming cyanobacteria other than PCC 7120
314 translated in all six reading frames (Jeff Elhai, personal communication) identified
315 putative PatS peptides in 10 of them (annotated only in one case, that of *Nostoc*
316 *punctiforme*, although the peptide of *Anabaena variabilis* would be identical to that
317 of PCC 7120). Besides PCC 7120 and *A. variabilis*, in two other strains PatS would
318 be 17-amino acid peptides with M¹ and M⁵; three strains could produce 15-amino
319 acid peptides with only one M start codon, and four other could produce longer
320 PatS peptides, two of them with one M aligning to M⁵ of PCC 7120. Thus, a
321 considerable variability in the N-terminal part of putative PatS peptides among
322 heterocyst-forming cyanobacteria is apparent, with a number of strains putatively
323 producing PatS peptides with extended N-terminal fragments.

324 Results from the study of strains producing PatS with insertions or amino
325 acid substitutions lead us to consider two different regions of the 17-residue
326 peptide in *Anabaena* sp. strain PCC 7120. In the N-terminal region, substitutions in
327 the second (in strain CSL90), third (in CSL91) or fourth (in CSL92) positions of
328 PatS lead to a decrease in (pro)heterocyst frequency, which is more severe in the
329 two latter cases (Fig. 5). The changes in V⁷ have strong effects on differentiation:

330 its substitution by A (in strain CSL93) impairs differentiation, and its substitution
331 by Q (in CSL51) abolishes differentiation, although this can be compensated in part
332 by introducing a V residue in the 5th position of the peptide (in CSL62). These
333 results imply that the modified versions of PatS produced in strains CSL90, CSL91,
334 CSL92, CSL93 and CSL51, as is also the case for those produced in CSL19, CSL21
335 and CSL22, inhibit the differentiation of the producing cells into heterocysts.
336 Although to a lesser extent, also the changes in N⁸ (strain CSL52) and F⁹ (strain
337 CSL53) inhibit differentiation. Whatever the mechanism the wild type uses for self-
338 immunity of the producing cells against PatS, it appears impaired in these mutant
339 strains. In contrast, the PatS inhibitory activity is retained in them. Thus, the 9-,
340 and specially the 7-residue N-terminal part of PatS is required for self-immunity of
341 the producing cells but not for PatS activity.

342 In the C-terminal region of PatS, whereas C¹⁰, E¹², G¹⁴ and R¹⁷ appear
343 important, R¹³, S¹⁵ and G¹⁶ are essential for the inhibitory function of PatS in cells
344 adjacent to the producing cells (Fig. 5). The *hetN* gene is also needed for wild-type
345 heterocyst patterning in *Anabaena* sp. strain PCC 7120, although its function is
346 evident in filaments growing steadily on N₂ rather than in filaments subjected to
347 nitrogen deprivation (Callahan and Buikema, 2001). A HetN-related product would be
348 produced by the mature heterocysts to inhibit neighboring cells from differentiating.
349 The 287-residue HetN polypeptide bears an internal ERGSGR sequence, of which
350 RGSGR has been shown to be essential for heterocyst patterning, and in which the two
351 R residues are essential to suppress heterocyst differentiation (Higa *et al.*, 2012). Thus,
352 some similarities may exist between the mechanism of action of PatS and that of HetN
353 (Khudyakov and Golden, 2004).

354 As mentioned above, it has been proposed that a PatS-related product
355 moves from the producing proheterocyst to the adjacent cells. We have detected
356 by immunofluorescence PatS-5 showing an accumulation of a PatS-5 containing
357 product in the cells adjacent to proheterocysts (Fig. 4). This represents a direct
358 evidence for intercellular transfer of a PatS peptide. In other bacteria, peptides that
359 have a role in the control of developmental processes have been identified, and in
360 some cases the biological function depends on events of peptide transport in and
361 out of the cells. A number of examples have been reported for *Bacillus* peptides
362 involved in the regulation of sporulation, quorum sensing and virulence, such as
363 PhrA and CSF pentapeptides that are produced by processing of precursor
364 molecules and secretion (Lazazzera *et al.*, 1997). The processed forms of both
365 peptides are transported into the cell by the oligopeptide permease SpoOK (OPP)
366 (Solomon *et al.*, 2011; Perego and Hoch, 1996). PhrA is synthesized as a 44-amino
367 acid molecule with an N-terminal hydrophobic domain and a C-terminal
368 hydrophilic region separated by a potential signal peptidase I cleavage site (which
369 would correspond to a V, H or A residue), implying that the carboxyl half of the
370 protein is secreted from the cell (Perego and Hoch, 1996). In the case of CSF, an
371 important role of the region comprising the 5 amino acids preceding the active
372 pentapeptide in directing cleavage of the precursor protein has been reported
373 (Laningan-Gerdes *et al.*, 2008). In the case of PatS, consistent with its small size, no
374 signal peptide could be recognized using different prediction programs (e.g.
375 SignalP 4.0; Petersen *et al.*, 2011), and no obvious matches to the pattern of signal
376 peptidase I (Paetzel *et al.*, 2002) could be recognized either. Thus, PatS would be
377 exported from the producing proheterocysts by a novel mechanism, which may
378 involve direction to the periplasm from which it could be imported by neighboring

379 vegetative cells, or direct cell-to-cell transfer through channels located in the
380 intercellular septa (Flores and Herrero, 2010).

381 The possibility that PatS were cleaved to generate an active smaller peptide
382 was consistent with all available data, but not finally proved. Previously, *patS4* to
383 *patS8* minigenes were expressed in *Anabaena* from promoters with different cell
384 specificity (Wu *et al.*, 2004). When *patS5* was expressed in proheterocysts in the
385 *patS* background, from either the *patS* promoter or the (pro)heterocyst-specific
386 *hepA* promoter, no or only a weak inhibition could be detected. These results are
387 consistent with those obtained with strain CSL45 described above, confirming that
388 PatS-5 expressed in proheterocysts is able to produce neither inhibition in the
389 producing cells nor cell-cell signaling. The fact that similar results were obtained
390 when the *P_{patS}-patS5* construct was placed either in the chromosome (this work) or
391 in a multicopy plasmid (Wu *et al.*, 2004) makes a low peptide dosage an unlikely
392 reason to explain lack of activity of the produced PatS-5. Moreover, we have shown
393 that in strain CSL45 PatS-5 is accumulated in the producing proheterocysts (Fig.
394 4). In contrast, PatS-8 (in strain CSL47), which includes all the residues that our
395 results have implicated in the inhibitory activity of PatS, appears to produce a
396 regulation similar to that produced by wild-type PatS. When expressed from the
397 copper-inducible *petE* promoter, which is active mainly in vegetative cells, *patS8*,
398 *patS7*, *patS6* and *patS5*, but not *patS4*, produced inhibition of heterocyst
399 differentiation both in the wild type and a *patS*-null mutant (Wu *et al.*, 2004).
400 Expression of *patS* or *patS5* from the *rbcl* promoter, which directs strong
401 expression only in vegetative cells, completely inhibits heterocyst formation both
402 in the wild type and the *patS* mutant (Wu *et al.*, 2004). Additionally, PatS-5 added
403 to the culture medium inhibits heterocyst differentiation (Yoon and Golden, 1998;

404 Wu *et al.*, 2004). Thus PatS-5, which is not active in the proheterocysts and would
405 not be exported from these cells, inhibits heterocyst differentiation when placed in
406 the vegetative cells. It appears that, in contrast to the receptor vegetative cells, the
407 producing proheterocysts are insensitive to the small processed peptides whereas,
408 as deduced from the phenotype of strains expressing peptides with point
409 substitutions in the N-terminal 9-amino acid stretch, they are sensitive to the
410 unprocessed PatS. In this regard, whether the processed peptides are accumulated
411 at different steps of the differentiation process in the producing and receptor cells,
412 and whether the mechanism of inhibition by the unprocessed and processed
413 peptides is different will merit future investigation.

414 Several reports have shown in vitro activity of synthetic PatS-5 at binding to
415 HetR and inhibition of HetR-binding to DNA (Huang *et al.*, 2004; Risser and
416 Callahan, 2007; Du *et al.*, 2012; Feldmann *et al.*, 2011). Binding to HetR was tighter
417 for PatS-6 (ERGSGR) than for PatS-5, and binding was tighter for PatS-5 than for
418 PatS-7 (DERGSGR), whereas no binding was detected for PatS-8 (CDERGSGR)
419 (Feldmann *et al.*, 2012). Thus, some differences could be found between the
420 relative affinities of the different peptides for in vitro binding to HetR and for their
421 activity of inhibition of heterocyst differentiation. The most striking of these
422 differences is that found with PatS-8, which does not appreciably bind to HetR in
423 vitro, but appears to be fully active in strain CSL47. It is possible that: (i) the
424 affinity for a molecular target (HetR) is influenced by additional conditions or
425 factors in vivo; (ii) the molecule exhibiting a tighter binding, or even a higher in
426 vivo activity when over-produced in the cyanobacterium (e.g. specifically in
427 vegetative cells), is not the best suited for a regulatory effect in vivo; (iii) the
428 presence of a M residue in the in vivo-produced, but not in the in vitro used,

429 peptides influences the studied parameters; (iv) in addition to HetR, other
430 molecular targets of PatS influence its role as inhibitor of heterocyst
431 differentiation. Although with the present data it is not possible to exclude that the
432 exported peptide could be further cleaved during the transfer or in the receptor
433 cells to render PatS-5, it is also possible that this is not the physiologically
434 significant inhibitory peptide.

435 In conclusion, our results are consistent with the model illustrated in Figure
436 5, in which PatS-17 is the product of the *patS* gene in the proheterocysts. This
437 polypeptide, which if accumulated appears to inhibit differentiation of the
438 producing cells, is not exported as such, but it is susceptible of cleavage to render a
439 smaller peptide derived from its C-terminal part and likely consisting of 8 amino
440 acids, which would be the morphogen transferred to the neighboring cells. In PatS,
441 K², A³, and I⁴ appear to be very important and V⁷ essential for PatS
442 processing/export, but the fact that expression of M-PatS-8 in proheterocysts (in
443 strain CSL47) leads to a wild-type heterocyst distribution implies that export from
444 proheterocysts to vegetative cells could also take place unlinked from processing.
445 Additionally, C¹⁰, E¹², G¹⁴ and R¹⁷ appear important and R¹³, S¹⁵ and G¹⁶ essential
446 for PatS activity of inhibition of differentiation.

447

448 **Experimental Procedures**

449 *Strains and growth conditions*

450 Growth conditions of *Anabaena* sp. (also known as *Nostoc* sp.) strain PCC 7120
451 were as described (López-Igual *et al.*, 2012a). Except for strain CSVT20, which was
452 grown without antibiotics, all the mutants listed in Table 1 were grown in medium

453 supplemented with streptomycin (Sm) and spectinomycin (Sp) at 5 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ each in
454 solid media and 2 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ each in liquid media. Growth rate constant
455 determinations were performed as in Valladares *et al.* (2011). Nitrogenase activity
456 was determined under oxic conditions in filaments incubated for 24 h in bubbled
457 cultures without nitrogen and without antibiotics (López-Igual *et al.*, 2012b).

458 *Construction of mutants*

459 To delete the *patS* gene, two DNA fragments, one encompassing sequences
460 upstream of the gene and the other including sequences downstream of the gene,
461 were amplified by PCR using DNA from *Anabaena* sp. strain PCC 7120 as template
462 and the primer pairs asl2301-8/asl2301-9 and asl2301-10/asl2301-11,
463 respectively (all oligodeoxynucleotide primers are listed in Table 3). The upstream
464 and downstream DNA fragments were cloned in pMBL-T (Dominion MBL, Spain),
465 sequenced and inserted together, in direct orientation, into pCSRO. This plasmid,
466 which is derived from pRL500 (Elhai and Wolk, 1988), can be mobilized by
467 conjugation and bears an $\text{Sm}^{\text{R}}/\text{Sp}^{\text{R}}$ determinant and the *sacB* gene for positive
468 selection. The plasmid produced, pCSVT51, bears cloned *Anabaena* DNA from the
469 *asl2301* locus with a deletion of 180 bp, which includes the whole *patS* gene.
470 Plasmid pCSVT51 was transferred to *Anabaena* sp. strain PCC 7120 by conjugation,
471 which was performed as described (Elhai *et al.*, 1997). Exconjugants were selected
472 by their resistance to Sm and Sp and double recombinants were then selected by
473 their resistance to sucrose. The clone isolated, CSVT20, lacked those 180 bp
474 including the *patS* gene.

475 For construction of fusions of the *gfp-mut2* gene to *patS*, two DNA
476 fragments were amplified, one using *Anabaena* DNA as template and primer pairs

477 asl2301-9/als2301-15 (for strain CSL19) and asl2301-9/asl2301-17 (for strain
478 CSL21), and the other using pCSAM135 (Flores *et al.*, 2007) as template and
479 primer pairs gfp-asl2301-1/gfp-asl2301-2 (for strain CSL19) and gfp-asl2301-
480 5/gfp-asl2301-6 (for strain CSL21). PCR products were cloned together in pMBL-T
481 producing pCSL29 and pCSL33, respectively. KpnI fragments from these plasmids
482 bearing the *gfp-mut2* gene were inserted into mobilizable vector pCSV3
483 (Valladares *et al.*, 2011) digested with the same enzyme, producing pCSL30 and
484 pCSL34, respectively.

485 For construction of a PatS-6His fusion (strain CSL22), a DNA fragment was
486 amplified using *Anabaena* DNA as template and primer pair asl2301-9/als2301-18,
487 and cloned in pMBL-T producing pCSL3. A KpnI fragment from this plasmid
488 carrying the *patS*-6His fusion was inserted into pCSV3 digested with the same
489 enzyme, producing pCSL36.

490 For construction of PatS point mutants and minigenes, a DNA fragment was
491 amplified using *Anabaena* DNA as template and primer pairs asl2301-9/asl2301-
492 32 to asl2301-49 (for strains CSL44 to CSL62), asl2301-9/asl2301-77 (for strain
493 CSL94) or asl2301-69/asl2301-71 or asl2301-72 (for strains CSL91 and CSL92,
494 respectively) and finally cloned into pCSV3 producing pCSL82 to pCSL95, pCSL110,
495 pCSL104, and pCSL105, respectively. For construction of strains CSL90 and CSL93,
496 DNA fragments, from 2771000 to 2771734 (coordinates of the strain PCC 7120
497 genomic sequence; Kaneko *et al.*, 2001), including nucleotide changes to produce
498 K²A and V⁷A substitutions, respectively, were synthesized (GeneArt®, Invitrogen)
499 and cloned into pCSV3 producing plasmids pCSL103 and pCSL106, respectively.

500 Plasmids pCSL30, pCSL34, pCSL36, pCSL38, pCSL82 to pCSL95, pCSL110,
501 pCSL104, pCSL105, pCSL103 and pCSL106 were transferred to the *patS* mutant,

502 strain CSV20, by conjugation (Elhai *et al.*, 1997). Clones resistant to Sm and Sp
503 were selected, and their genomic structure in the *patS* region was tested by PCR
504 with primers asl2301-74 (which lies outside of the construct, 5' from it) and
505 asl2301-75 (which lies inside the region deleted in strain CSV20) or asl2301-76
506 (which lies outside of the construct, 3' from it) to check recombination in the
507 correct place and segregation of the *patS*-mutant chromosomes. Additionally,
508 except for CSL19 and CSL21, the *patS* ORF was sequenced in all the *Anabaena*
509 strains generated in this work.

510 *Microscopy*

511 For light microscopy, filaments grown in BG11₀ + ammonium medium (in the
512 presence of Sm and Sp for the mutants) were harvested, washed with nitrogen-free
513 (BG11₀) medium and incubated for 24 h in bubbled cultures at 30°C in the light. At
514 least 300 cells or 100 intervals were counted for each strain in each of three
515 independent experiments. Dividing cells were counted as two cells. For staining
516 (pro)heterocysts, cell suspensions were mixed (1:10) with a 1% Alcian Blue
517 (Sigma) solution (López-Igual *et al.*, 2012b). For confocal microscopy, samples
518 from cultures of *Anabaena* sp. set atop solidified medium (BG11₀ + ammonium or
519 BG11₀) were visualized using a Leica HCX PLAN-APO 63X 1.4 NA oil immersion
520 objective attached to a Leica TCS SP2 confocal laser-scanning microscope. GFP was
521 excited using 488-nm irradiation from an argon ion laser. Fluorescence from GFP
522 was monitored by collection across windows of 500-540 nm.

523 For immunofluorescence detection of the PatS-5 sequence, 300 µl of liquid
524 cultures (containing 2 to 3 µg of chlorophyll *a*/ml) were placed atop poly-L-lysine
525 precoated microscope slides and covered with a 45-µm pore-size Millipore filter.

526 After that, the filter was removed and the slide was let to dry at room temperature
527 and, then, immersed in 70% ethanol during 30 min at -20 °C and dried 10 min in
528 an oven at 80 °C. The cells were then washed twice by covering the slide with PBS-
529 T buffer (140 mM NaCl, 1.5 mM KH₂PO₄, 2.7 mM KCl [pH 7.4], Tween-20 [0.05
530 p/v]) (2 min each time, room temperature) and treated with blocking buffer (5%
531 milk powder in PBS-T, 15 min). The cells on the slides were then incubated with a
532 primary anti-PatS-5 antibody solution (rabbit polyclonal antibody raised against
533 synthetic RGSGR, Cambridge Research Biochemicals, purified by affinity
534 chromatography and 1:100 diluted in blocking buffer) for 90 min, washed three
535 times with PBS-T, incubated 45 min in the dark with secondary anti-rabbit
536 antibody conjugated to fluorescein isithiocyanate (FITC) (Sigma, 1:500 dilution in
537 PBS-T) and washed three times with PBS-T. After dried, several drops of FluorSave
538 (Carl Biochem) were added atop, covered with a cover slip, sealed with nail lack
539 and let dry overnight at 4 °C. Fluorescence was imaged using a Leica DM6000B
540 fluorescence microscope and an ORCA-ER camera (Hamamatsu). Fluorescence was
541 monitored using a FITC L5 filter (excitation, band-pass [BP] 480/40 filter;
542 emission, BP 527/30 filter) and quantified analyzing in each cell “the mean gray
543 value” of the ImageJ software (<http://imagej.nih.gov/ij>).

544

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- 662
- 663

664 **Figure legends**

665

666 **Fig. 1.** Scheme of the genetic constructs used in this work. A 180 bp DNA fragment
667 containing the *patS* gene was deleted from the chromosome of *Anabaena* sp. strain PCC
668 7120 to produce strain CSVT20. The latter was used as parental strain to introduce a
669 wild-type or an altered *patS* gene (*patS**). A DNA fragment containing 672 bp of the
670 region 5' from *patS* and the *patS** sequence was transferred, cloned in plasmid pCSV3
671 that lacks an origin of replication for *Anabaena* sp., to strain CSVT20. Single
672 recombinants that had inserted the construct in the chromosome by a single
673 recombination event were selected as Sm^R/Sp^R clones, which represented the different
674 CSL strains.

675 **Fig. 2.** Expression of PatS-GFP translational fusions. *Anabaena* producing a
676 polypeptide with the GFP inserted after the first (strain CSL21) or the second (strain
677 CSL19) M residue of PatS or, as a reference, a P_{*patS-gfp*} transcriptional fusion in the
678 strain PCC 7120 α megaplasmid (CSVM17) were grown in ammonium-containing
679 medium and incubated in the absence of combined nitrogen for the indicated times. The
680 filaments were visualized by confocal microscopy. Merged bright field/green GFP
681 fluorescence micrographs are shown.

682 **Fig. 3.** Heterocyst distribution in *Anabaena* sp. strain PCC 7120 and mutant strains.
683 Except for strains PCC 7120 and CSVT20 (Δ *patS*), the PatS polypeptide produced in
684 each strain is indicated. In the PatS polypeptides containing point amino acid
685 substitutions, the introduced amino acid(s) are highlighted. In strain CSL22, the
686 diamond denotes the place of insertion of a 6-His sequence in the PatS polypeptide. The
687 percentage of heterocysts formed by each strain is also indicated. Heterocyst
688 distribution could be analyzed accurately only in strains showing more than 5%

689 heterocysts. The micrograph shows filaments of strain PCC 7120 in which
690 proheterocysts and heterocysts appear blue after Alcian Blue staining.

691 **Fig. 4.** Immunofluorescence detection of PatS-5. Filaments of the indicated strains (for
692 genotypes, see Table 1) grown in bubbled ammonium-containing cultures were
693 incubated for 8 h in bubbled medium lacking combined nitrogen and used in an
694 immunofluorescence test with antibodies raised against the RGSGR pentapeptide. (A)
695 Visualization of filaments subjected to immunodetection of PatS-5. Bright field,
696 fluorescence and bright field/fluorescence merge micrographs are shown from left to
697 right. Arrowheads point to proheterocysts. (B) Quantification of immunofluorescence
698 from PatS in filaments of strains PCC 7120 and CSL45. The fluorescence detected
699 (arbitrary units) in proheterocysts (h) and their neighboring cells (n1 to n7, the cell in
700 position n1 is adjacent to the proheterocyst) in each strain is represented. The values
701 represented are the mean of the fluorescence recorded in each position (301 cells from
702 three different cultures were counted for PCC 7120, and 185 cells for CSL45) less the
703 mean of the fluorescence measured in strain CSVT20 (96 cells), which was used as
704 background levels. Bars indicate the standard deviations of the mean. *t*-Tests indicate
705 that in strain PCC 7120 the fluorescence value for the proheterocysts is different
706 ($P < 0.01$) than those from their neighbors.

707 **Fig. 5.** The *patS* gene is expressed as a 17-residue polypeptide including an N-terminal
708 part involved in PatS processing and a C-terminal part required for PatS regulatory
709 function. An *Anabaena* strain carrying a mutation of a residue labeled black expresses a
710 phenotype similar to the wild-type phenotype. A strain carrying a mutation of a residue
711 labeled red exhibits less heterocyst differentiation than the wild type. A strain carrying a
712 mutation of a residue labeled green exhibits more heterocyst differentiation than the
713 wild type.

714 **Table 1.** Phenotype of *Anabaena* sp. PCC 7120 mutants producing different PatS peptides.

Strain	Mutant version of PatS	Heterocysts (%)	Mean interval size	Contiguous heterocysts (%)
PCC 7120		10.31 ± 0.64	9.67 ± 0.26	4.36 ± 0.58
CSVT20	Δ [180 bp]	19.00 ± 2.12	5.69 ± 0.38	20.81 ± 5.13
CSL19	MKAIM [GFP] LVNFCDERGSGR	0.54 ± 0.33	-	0
CSL21	M [GFP] KAIMLVNFCDERGSGR	2.94 ± 0.82	-	0
CSL22	MKAIM [H₆] LVNFCDERGSGR	5.31 ± 0.76	13.18 ± 0.59	2.27 ± 2.27
CSL45	MRGSGR	20.29 ± 1.58	5.59 ± 0.47	11.30 ± 0.96
CSL46	MERGSGR	13.79 ± 1.12	7.40 ± 0.36	21.11 ± 2.92
CSL94	MDERGSGR	10.01 ± 0.61	11.12 ± 0.55	12.46 ± 3.99
CSL47	MCDERGSGR	9.02 ± 0.85	10.83 ± 0.51	4.59 ± 0.09
CSL48	MKAIMLVNFCDERGSGR	12.39 ± 0.70	10.40 ± 0.38	6.01 ± 0.66
CSL44	A KAIMLVNFCDERGSGR	18.67 ± 0.69	5.55 ± 0.01	25.55 ± 6.09
CSL90	M AAIMLVNFCDERGSGR	4.47 ± 0.77	-	0
CSL91	MK Q IMLVNFCDERGSGR	2.10 ± 0.95	-	0
CSL92	MKA Q MLVNFCDERGSGR	1.97 ± 1.09	-	0
CSL49	MKA I ALVNFCDERGSGR	10.56 ± 1.30	10.69 ± 0.78	6.73 ± 3.05
CSL50	MKAIM Q VNFCDERGSGR	10.09 ± 0.76	10.83 ± 0.29	3.75 ± 2.15
CSL93	MKAIM L ANFCDERGSGR	3.43 ± 0.41	-	0
CSL51	MKAIM L QNFCDERGSGR	0.03 ± 0.03	-	0
CSL62	MKA I VLQNFCDERGSGR	6.01 ± 1.82	17.63 ± 1.68	0
CSL52	MKAIM L VEFCDERGSGR	8.35 ± 1.08	10.32 ± 0.53	1.33 ± 1.33
CSL53	MKAIMLVN Q CDERGSGR	7.45 ± 1.65	14.01 ± 0.97	0
CSL54	MKAIMLVNF A DERGSGR	10.24 ± 0.71	9.85 ± 0.24	11.15 ± 3.08
CSL55	MKAIMLVNF C QERGSGR	12.02 ± 2.05	9.68 ± 0.77	4.76 ± 2.10
CSL56	MKAIMLVNF C D A RGSGR	11.46 ± 0.92	8.12 ± 0.21	9.08 ± 4.88
CSL57	MKAIMLVNF C D E A G SGR	22.75 ± 2.33	4.67 ± 0.12	25.16 ± 5.24
CSL59	MKAIMLVNF C D E R A SGR	15.30 ± 2.38	7.47 ± 0.46	8.08 ± 1.82
CSL58	MKAIMLVNF C D E R G A G R	24.62 ± 3.79	4.85 ± 0.46	24.27 ± 4.90
CSL60	MKAIMLVNF C D E R G S A R	16.92 ± 1.52	4.98 ± 0.17	26.17 ± 4.03
CSL61	MKAIMLVNF C D E R G S G A	16.03 ± 1.56	8.14 ± 0.21	9.75 ± 1.98

The amino acid sequence of the PatS peptide produced by the altered *patS* gene present in each strain is shown (the wild-type peptide sequence is MKAIMLVNFCDERGSGR). When appropriate, the location of the inserted GFP protein or 6-His tag is indicated between brackets. In the case of substitution mutations, the amino acid introduced is written in bold. All the mutant strains were generated using strain CSVT20 as parental. Heterocyst frequency (as percentage of total cells) is indicated for each strain. The mean size of vegetative cell intervals between heterocysts and the percentage of contiguous heterocysts (interval size = 0, percentage of total intervals) have been calculated from the data in Figure 3.

Table 2. Phenotypic characteristics of *Anabaena* sp. PCC 7120 wild-type strain (PCC 7120), a *patS* deletion strain (CSVT20) and mutants producing PatS-tagged peptides.

Strain	Nitrogenase activity nmol ($\mu\text{g chlorophyll } a$) ⁻¹ h ⁻¹	Growth rate (day ⁻¹)	
		Ammonium	Dinitrogen
PCC 7120	19.69 ± 0.68	0.53 ± 0.02	0.45 ± 0.01
CSVT20	12.02 ± 0.86	0.49 ± 0.04	0.36 ± 0.03
CSL19	0.02 ± 0.01	0.58 ± 0.04	0.09 ± 0.03
CSL21	0.63 ± 0.10	0.53 ± 0.04	0.16 ± 0.05
CSL22	2.46 ± 1.13	0.64 ± 0.02	0.28 ± 0.03

Data are the mean and the standard deviation of the mean of the results of two to four experiments performed with independent cultures (nitrogenase) or of four independent cultures (growth rates). Genotypes are indicated in Table 1.

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Table 3. Oligodeoxynucleotide primers used in this work.

Primer	Sequence (5' → 3')
asl2301-8	CATACCCAATTGCATCTTCTCATCATCAGTCTT
asl2301-9	CTGGGCAGTTAGTACGGAAAGT
asl2301-10	TTAGAGCGCAGTAGGGAAAAG
asl2301-11	GATGCAATTGGGTATGGCGTTGATGT
asl2301-15	TTCTTCTCCTTTACTCATAATTGCCTTCAT
asl2301-16	TTCTTCTCCTTTACTTCTACCACTACCGCG
asl2301-17	TTCTTCTCCTTTACTCATAATCTTAAAATC
asl2301-18	CTATCTACCACTACCGCGCTCATCACAGAAATTCACTAAGTGGTGGTGGTGGTGGTGCAT AATTGCCTTCATAATCTTAAAATC
asl2301-19	CTAATGATGATGATGATGATGTCTACCACTACCGCGCTC
asl2301-32	CTATCTACCACTACCGCGCTCATCACAGAAATTCACTAACATAATTGCCTTCGCAA
asl2301-33	CTATCTACCACTACCGCGCATAATCTTA
asl2301-35	CTATCTACCACTACCGCGCTCATCACACATAATCTTAAAATCG
asl2301-36	CTATCTACCACTACCGCGCTC
asl2301-37	CTATCTACCACTACCGCGCTCATCACAGAAATTCACTAACGCAATTGCC
asl2301-38	CTATCTACCACTACCGCGCTCATCACAGAAATTCACTTGCATAAT
asl2301-39	CTATCTACCACTACCGCGCTCATCACAGAAATTTCTGTAACA
asl2301-40	CTATCTACCACTACCGCGCTCATCACAGAATTCCTACTA
asl2301-41	CTATCTACCACTACCGCGCTCATCACACTGATTCA
asl2301-42	CTATCTACCACTACCGCGCTCATCAGCGAAAT
asl2301-43	CTATCTACCACTACCGCGCTCTTGACAGA
asl2301-44	CTATCTACCACTACCGCGCGCATC
asl2301-45	CTATCTACCACTACCGGCCTCATCA
asl2301-46	CTATCTACCACTAGCGCGCTCA
asl2301-48	CTATCTAGCACTACCGCGCTCA
asl2301-49	CTATGCACCACTACCGCGCTCA
asl2301-71	TTACTACTGCAGCTATCTACCACTACCGCGCTCATCACAGAAATTCACTAACATAATTTGCT TCAT
asl2301-72	TTACTACTGCAGCTATCTACCACTACCGCGCTCATCACAGAAATTCACTAACATTTGTGCCT T
asl2301-74	CAGGGTCAGTATTGTTTCGG
asl2301-75	CACCATTCAATTGCACCATCAG
asl2301-76	TCGGTGAATTACTTTTCAACAG
asl2301-77	CTATCTACCACTACCGCGCTCATCCATAATCTTAAAATC
gfp-asl2301-1	ATGAAGGCAATTATGAGTAAAGGAGAAGAA
gfp-asl2301-2	CTATCTACCACTACCGCGCTCATCACAGAAATTCACTAATTTGTATAGTTCATC
gfp-asl2301-5	GATTTTAAGATTATGAGTAAAGGAGAAGAA
gfp-asl2301-6	CTATCTACCACTACCGCGCTCATCACAGAAATTCACTAACATAATTGCCTTTTGTATAGT TCATCCATGCC

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Corrales-Guerrero *et al.* Figure 1

Corrales-Guerrero *et al.* Figure 2

Corrales-Guerrero *et al.* Figure 3

Corrales-Guerrero *et al.* Figure 4

Corrales-Guerrero *et al.* Figure 5

